

Mitochondria dysfunction induced by decyl-TPP mitochondriotropic antioxidant based on caffeic acid AntiOx_{CIN}₆ sensitizes cisplatin lung anticancer therapy due to a remodeling of energy metabolism

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ABSTRACT

The pharmacological interest in mitochondria is very relevant since these crucial organelles are involved in the pathogenesis of multiple diseases, such as cancer. In order to modulate cellular redox/oxidative balance and enhance mitochondrial function, numerous polyphenolic derivatives targeting mitochondria have been developed. Still, due to the drug resistance emergence in several cancer therapies, significant efforts are being made to develop drugs that combine the induction of mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming with the ability to generate reactive oxygen species, taking into consideration the varying metabolic profiles of different cell types. We previously developed a mitochondria-targeted antioxidant (AntiOx_{CIN}₆) by linking caffeic acid to lipophilic triphenylphosphonium cation through a 10-carbon aliphatic chain. The antioxidant activity of AntiOx_{CIN}₆ has been documented but how the mitochondriotropic compound impact energy metabolism of both normal and cancer cells remains unknown. We demonstrated that AntiOx_{CIN}₆ increased antioxidant defense system in HepG2 cells, although ROS clearance was ineffective. Consequently, AntiOx_{CIN}₆ significantly decreased mitochondrial function and morphology, culminating in a decreased capacity in complex I-driven ATP production without affecting cell viability. These alterations were accompanied by an increase in glycolytic fluxes. Additionally, we demonstrate that AntiOx_{CIN}₆ sensitized A549 adenocarcinoma cells for CIS-induced apoptotic cell death, while AntiOx_{CIN}₆ appears to cause metabolic changes or a redox pre-conditioning on lung MRC-5

Abbreviations: 2DG, 2-Deoxy-D-glucose; AA, antimycin A; ADP, adenosine diphosphate; AMP, adenosine monophosphate; ATP, adenosine triphosphate; CA, caffeic acid; CAT, catalase; CIS, Cisplatin; ECAR, extracellular acidification rate; ETC, electron transport chain; GAPBA, GA binding protein transcription factor subunit alpha; G6PD, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase; GPx, glutathione peroxidase; GR, glutathione reductase; GSH, reduced glutathione; GSSG, glutathione disulfide; HCAs, hydroxycinnamic acids; HMOX1, Heme oxygenase 1; IMS, intermembrane space; KEAP1, kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1; MDA, malondialdehyde; MEN, menadione; MIM, mitochondrial inner membrane; MOM, mitochondrial outer membrane; mtROS, mitochondrial reactive oxygen species; NAD(P)H, reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; NQO1, NAD(P)H dehydrogenase (quinone) 1; NRF1, nuclear respiratory factor 1; Nrf2, nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2; NSCLC, non-small-cell lung cancer; OCR, oxygen consumption rate; OXPHOS, oxidative phosphorylation; PGC-1 α , Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1 α ; PHSF, primary human skin fibroblasts; ROS, reactive oxygen species; ROT, rotenone; SOD1 CuZn, superoxide dismutase (non-mitochondrial); SOD2 Mn, superoxide dismutase (mitochondrial); TFAM, Transcription Factor A, Mitochondria; TMRM, tetramethylrhodamine methyl ester; TPP+, triphenylphosphonium cation; VDAC, voltage-dependent anion channel; $\Delta\psi_m$, mitochondrial transmembrane electric potential; γ -GCS, gamma-Glutamylcysteine synthetase.

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fibroblasts, conferring protection against cisplatin. We propose that length and hydrophobicity of the C10-TPP⁺ alkyl linker play a significant role in inducing mitochondrial and cellular toxicity, while the presence of the antioxidant caffeic acid appears to be responsible for activating cytoprotective pathways.

1. Introduction

Caffeic acid (CA) is a phenolic acid that can be exogenously obtained through human diet and whose antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antitumor properties have been extensively explored [1]. Caffeic acid can prevent and minimize oxidative damage, acting primarily as ROS scavenger and chelating agent, or indirectly by up-regulating endogenous antioxidant defenses [2]. Conversely, caffeic acid can also act as a prooxidant, a property that is intrinsically related with chemical structure, *in situ* concentration, and the cellular redox environment [3,4]. Moreover, the modulation of mitochondrial processes (interactions with oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) complexes, ATP synthesis, mitochondrial transmembrane potential ($\Delta\psi_m$), and mitochondrial biogenesis) has been extensively described by polyphenolic phytochemicals [5,6].

Mitochondria are subcellular compartments playing a crucial role in both survival and cell death. Although the generation of mitochondrial

ROS (mtROS) as a by-product of OXPHOS is essential to regulate signaling pathways, exacerbated mtROS levels compromise mitochondrial function and induce oxidative damage [7]. The involvement of mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in multiple pathophysiological conditions, including cancer has been extensively studied [8,9] making these organelles a promising target for therapeutic strategies. The attachment of lipophilic triphenylphosphonium (TPP⁺) cation through the conjugation with an alkyl linker (C_n-TPP) [10] was used to develop several TPP⁺-derived mitochondria-targeted polyphenolic derivatives including MitoResveratrol, MitoCurcumin, MitoQuercetin, Mito-Honokiol, Mito-lonidamine and MitoGentisic, mostly to destabilize mitochondrial function exhibiting antiproliferative effects rather than a cytoprotective activity on different cell models [9,11–15].

Despite the significant scientific endeavors to develop highly selective and effective anticancer drugs, drug resistance remains a significant challenge in many cancer therapies, including lung cancer [16,17]. This resistance can arise due to the unique metabolic profiles of cancer cells,

Fig. 1. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on HepG2 cells antioxidant defense system. (A) Chemical structure of the mitochondria-targeted hydroxycinnamic acid antioxidant AntiOxClN₆. (B) Effect of menadione (50 μM; 4 h) on cell metabolic activity in the absence or presence of increasing concentrations of AntiOxClN₆ for 48 h. (C) Time-dependent variations on fluorescence signal of MitSOX-oxidation products in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM). (D) α-tocopherol (vitamin E) levels, (E) GSH/GSSG ratio, (F) Glutathione reductase (GR) and (G) Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity in HepG2 treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h). Representative Western blot result and protein content of (H) γ-GCS, (I) TRX1, (J) SOD1, (L) catalase and β-actin (cytosolic marker) in whole-cell homogenates from cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h). This blot was inverted and contrast-optimized for visualization purposes. Quantification of the bands was performed using the original blots. Quantification of protein levels in four different assays was normalized to β-actin levels and to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). (K) Superoxide dismutase (SOD) and (M) catalase (CAT) activity in cell homogenates after treatment with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h). Data are means ± SEM of 3–5 independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the CTL condition (CTL = 100 %). In panel D, the results are expressed as pmol of vitamin E/μg protein, while in panel F, G and M results expressed in international units of enzyme per microgram of protein (U/μg protein). Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student's *t*-test to compare two mean values and the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * (*p* < 0.05). Significant differences between menadione and AntiOxClN₆ (0.62, 1.25 and 2.5 μM) are indicated by ### (*p* < 0.0005), #### (*p* < 0.0001).

which can vary across different individuals and even within the same tumor [18]. Recent studies have revealed that redirecting cellular energy metabolism towards glycolysis can offer additional benefits in overcoming the aforementioned drug resistance problem. For instance, the anticancer drug etoposide increases lactate secretion by shifting cellular metabolism toward glycolysis in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) [19]. Similarly, an increased mitochondrial mass, and therefore OXPHOS function, was described to be related with resistance mechanism to cisplatin treatment in NSCLC. This valuable knowledge can be used for the development of adjuvant therapies through the use of PGC-1 α or mitochondrial inhibitors [20]. In fact, mitochondrial pharmacology has been used against lung tumorigenesis. Mito-Honokiol and Mito-lonidamine prevented cancer development, progression, and metastasis in Benzo(A)Pyrene-induced lung tumor model in A/J mice by inhibiting complex-I- and complex-II-induced mitochondrial respiration and AKT/mTOR/p70S6K signaling in lung tumor cells [21].

We previously developed a mitochondria-targeted antioxidant based on CA (AntiOxCIN₆) (Fig. 1A) by linking the antioxidant core to lipophilic TPP⁺ through a 10-carbon aliphatic chain presenting strong antioxidant and iron chelation properties [22]. The antioxidant properties of AntiOxCIN₆ conferred cell death protection in human HepG2 and differentiated SH-SY5Y cells, a process that was accompanied by a moderated increment of ROS levels and maintenance of intracellular GSH homeostasis [22–24]. Despite the data obtained suggesting that AntiOxCIN₆ can also act as prooxidant under certain conditions, its effects on cellular energy metabolism were not studied in detail, namely in tumor cells.

In our current study, we conducted an in-depth examination of the cellular mechanisms by which AntiOxCIN₆ exerts both cytotoxic and cytoprotective effects. By elucidating these mechanisms, we aimed to evaluate the potential of AntiOxCIN₆ as a therapeutic agent for specific pathological conditions, including cancer.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Chemical and reagents

Cell culture medium, medium components, chemicals, and reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) unless otherwise specified.

2.2. Synthesis of AntiOxCIN₆

The synthesis, purification and spectroscopic characterization of the mitochondriotropic AntiOxCIN₆ was described previously [22].

2.3. Cell culture

Human hepatocellular carcinoma HepG2 cells (85011430, ECACC, UK) were cultured in low-glucose medium composed by Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; D5030, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) supplemented with 5 mM glucose, sodium bicarbonate (3.7 g/L), HEPES (1.19 g/L), L-glutamine (0.876 g/L), sodium pyruvate (0.11 g/L), 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1 % penicillin–streptomycin 100x solution. Human lung fibroblasts (MRC-5) (ATCC, Barcelona, Spain) and human adenocarcinoma alveolar basal epithelial cells (A549) (ATCC, Barcelona, Spain) cells were cultured in a high-glucose medium composed by Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; D5648), supplemented with sodium pyruvate (0.11 g/L), sodium bicarbonate (1.8 g/L) and 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1 % of antibiotic penicillin–streptomycin 100 x solution. LHON mutant cybrids (HCT22 cells) were a kind gift from Drs. Valerio Carelli and Andrea Martinuzzi [34]. These cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium containing 2 mM glutamine and 100 mM sodium pyruvate (DMEM, Corning). The medium was further supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS), 50 μ g/mL uridine and 1 % antibiotics (penicillin/streptomycin). All cells

were cultured under 5 % CO₂ atmosphere at 37 °C and passaged by trypsinization when reaching 80–90 % confluence. All experiments were performed in cultures in log phase growth.

2.4. Cell culture conditions and treatment

HepG2 cells were seeded at a density of 4.5×10^4 cells/cm² and grown for 24 h to reach 70–80 % confluency. Cells were then treated in the presence of the mitochondriotropic antioxidant AntiOxCIN₆ (2.5 μ M) or vehicle 0.0025 % (v/v) DMSO. Lung adenocarcinoma A549 cells and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts were seeded at a density of 4×10^4 cells/cm² or 2×10^4 cells/cm² respectively and grown for 24 h to reach 60–70 % confluency. A549 and MRC-5 were then incubated with cisplatin (10 μ M), AntiOxCIN₆ (3.1 μ M) or vehicle 0.0031 % (v/v) DMSO.

2.5. Cell metabolic viability

The resazurin reduction assay was used to assess the metabolic cell viability [43].

2.6. Mitochondrial superoxide anion detection

Mitochondrial superoxide anion was assessed through MitoSOX Red (M36008, ThermoFisher Scientific) assay [43].

2.7. Measurement of α -tocopherol (vitamin E) content

Extraction and separation of reduced α -tocopherol (vitamin E) from cells were performed by following a previously described method [25] as previously described [43].

2.8. Measurement of glutathione (GSH) and glutathione disulfide (GSSG) levels

GSH and GSSG levels were determined with fluorescence detection after reaction of the supernatant containing H₃PO₄/NaH₂PO₄–EDTA or H₃PO₄/NaOH, respectively, of the deproteinized homogenate solution with ophthalaldehyde (OPT), pH 8.0 [26] as previously described [43].

2.9. Western blotting analysis

Protein content levels were semi-quantitatively analyzed using gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) of whole-cell homogenates, from HepG2 cells treated with AntiOxCIN₆, followed by Western blotting with antibodies directed against the denatured form of γ -GCS_c (1:1000, sc-390811, Santa Cruz Biotechnology), G6PD (1:1000, sc-67165, Santa Cruz Biotechnology), Pyruvate dehydrogenase cocktail (1:1000, ab110416, Abcam), Hexokinase II (1:1000, cs2867, Cell Signaling), PKM2 (1:1000, cs4053, Cell Signaling), LDHA (1:1000, cs3582, Cell Signaling), Oxidative Stress Defense cocktail (1:200, ab179843, Abcam), Membrane Integrity cocktail (1:1000, ab110414, Abcam), Phospho-AMPK α (1:1000, cs2525, Cell Signaling), AMPK α (1:1000, cs5831, Cell Signaling) and β -Actin (1:5000, MAB1501, Milipore). β -Actin was used as housekeeping protein as no treatment-related changes in the protein levels were observed. Once incubation was completed, membranes were washed with TBST and incubated at room temperature with anti-rabbit (1:5000, 1677074S, Cell Signaling) or anti-mouse (1:5000, 1677076S, Cell Signaling) HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies, as previously described [43].

2.10. Measurement of glutathione disulfide reductase (GR) activity

Glutathione reductase activity was determined using GSSG as a substrate and monitoring its reduction to GSH through quantification of NADPH oxidation at 340 nm in a thermostated spectrophotometer UVIKON 933 UV/Visible, at 37 °C, as previously described [43].

2.11. Measurement of total superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity

Total SOD activity was measured by using a SOD activity assay kit (SOD activity Enzo Life Sciences, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.12. Measurement of catalase (CAT) activity

Catalase activity was followed by the variation of H₂O₂ absorbance at 240 nm during 2.5 min, with a readout each 15 s using a Cytation3 multi-mode microplate reader (BioTek Instruments, Inc., Winooski, VT, USA) [27], as previously described [43].

2.13. Measurement of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity

Glutathione peroxidase activity was evaluated by spectrophotometry using *tert*-butylperoxide as a substrate, monitoring the formation of oxidized glutathione, through the quantification of the oxidation of NADPH to NADP⁺ at 340 nm [28], as previously described [43].

2.14. Cellular oxygen consumption measurements

Cellular oxygen consumption was measured at 37 °C using a Seahorse XFe96 Extracellular Flux Analyzer (Agilent Scientific Instruments, California, USA), as previously described [43].

2.15. Mitochondrial transmembrane electric potential measurements

Vital confocal fluorescent microscopy was used to visualize alterations in mitochondrial electric potential polarization and network distribution in HepG2 cells pre-coated (collagen I 0.15 mg/mL) in μ -Slide 8 well ibiTreat Ibidi (2×10^4 /cm²) and incubated with fluorescent dyes tetramethylrhodamine (TMRM) (100 nM, Catalogue T668, ThermoFisher Scientific) and Hoechst 33342 (1 μ g/mL, Catalogue H1399, ThermoFisher Scientific) for mitochondrial network and nuclei, respectively, as previously described [43].

2.16. Mitochondrial DNA copy number measurements

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) copy number in HepG2 cells was measured using quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR), as previously described [43]. To estimate the mtDNA copy number relative to nuclear genomes, the number of copies of cytochrome *B* template was divided by the number of copies of beta-2 microglobulin template.

Table 1

Informative table on primers utilized for transcript amplification.

Gene	mRNA Sequence Name	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer
ATP5G1	Homo sapiens ATP synthase, H + transporting, mitochondrial Fo complex, subunit C1 (subunit 9) (ATP5G1), transcript variant 2, mRNA.	GGCTAAAGCTGGGAGACTGAAA	GTGGGAAGTTGCTGTAGGAAGG
COX4I1	Homo sapiens cytochrome c oxidase subunit IV isoform 1 (COX4I1), mRNA.	GAGAAAGTCGAGTTGTATCGCA	GCTTCTGCCACATGATAACGA
CY5C	Homo sapiens cytochrome c, somatic (CY5C), mRNA.	CGTTGAAAAGGGAGGCAAGC	TCCCCAGATGATGCCITTTGTC
FIS1	Homo sapiens fission, mitochondrial 1 (FIS1), mRNA.	AGCGGGATTACGTCTTCTACC	CATGCCACGAGTCCATCTTT
GABPA	Homo sapiens GA binding protein transcription factor, alpha subunit 60 kDa (GABPA), transcript variant 1, mRNA.	GGAACAGAACAGGAAACAATG	CTCATAGTTTCATCGTAGGCTTA
MFN2	Homo sapiens mitofusin 2 (MFN2), transcript variant 1, mRNA	AGCTACACTGGCTCCAACCTG	AACCGGCTTTATTCCTGAGCA
ND5	h_ND5 (12337–14148)	AGTTACAATCGGCATCAACCAA	CCGGGAGCACATAAATAGTATGG
NRF1	Homo sapiens nuclear respiratory factor 1 (NRF1), transcript variant 1, mRNA.	TTGAGTCTAATGCATCTATCCG	TACTTACGCACCACATTCTC
OPA1	Homo sapiens optic atrophy 1 (autosomal dominant) (OPA1), transcript variant 1, mRNA.	GCTCTAAACCATTGTAAACCTTGT	TTCTCTAATCGCCTAACTTCAGT
PPARGC1A	Homo sapiens peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma, coactivator 1 alpha (PPARGC1A), mRNA.	GCGAAGAGTATTGTCAACAG	TTGGTTTGGCTGTAAAGTGT
TBP	Homo sapiens TATA box binding protein (TBP), transcript variant 1, mRNA.	CGAATATAATCCCAAGCGTTTTCG	AGCTGGAAAACCCAACTTCTGT
TFAM	Homo sapiens transcription factor A, mitochondrial (TFAM), transcript variant 1	GTTTCTCCGAAGCATGTG	GGTAAATACACAAAACCTGAAGG
UQCRC2	Homo sapiens ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase core protein II (UQCRC2), mRNA	TTTCAGCAATTTAGGAACCCACC	GGTCACACTTAATTTGCCACCAA

2.17. Gene expression measurements

Transcript analysis in HepG2 cells was assessed by performing quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR), as previously described [43]. RT-PCR was performed using the SsoFast Eva Green Supermix, in a CFX96 real time-PCR system (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), with the primers defined in Table 1, at 500 nM. Amplification of 25 ng was performed with an initial cycle of 30 s at 95 °C, followed by 40 cycles of 5 s at 95 °C plus 5 s at 60 °C. At the end of each cycle, Eva Green fluorescence was recorded to enable determination of Cq. After amplification, melting temperature of the PCR products was determined by performing melting curves, as previously described [43].

2.18. Measurement of mitochondrial ATP formation

For the measurement of complex I-driven ATP synthesis, cybrid cells were used. The cells were seeded at 5×10^4 cells/well in 100 μ L of culture medium, in a white opaque-bottom, 96-well plate coated with poly-D-Lysine (Corning) and were incubated at 37 °C overnight. Anti-OxClN₆ dissolved in serum-free medium and 100 μ L of 2 x agent solution was added to the cells. Following this, the treated cells were incubated for 22 h at 37 °C. Then, 100 μ L of conditioned medium was removed from the wells and 100 μ L of medium containing rotenone (2x final concentration) was added to the cells. After 2 h of incubation at 37 °C, the medium from the plates was aspirated using an automatic plate washer (Biotek). Complex I driven ATP synthesis was measured following the protocol of Yoshida and Fujikawa [29], with minor modifications. Briefly, after aspirating the conditioned medium, Anti-OxClN₆ and rotenone-treated cells were permeabilized using streptolysin O (SLO). The plasma membrane permeabilization was done in two steps. Firstly, SLO was allowed to attach the plasma membrane at 0 °C. Then, the extra SLO was removed and subsequently the attached SLO was activated at 37 °C for permeabilization. Plate washes were minimized to prevent the cell loss. The permeabilized cells were incubated for 15 min with complex I substrate, malate (5 mM) and pyruvate (5 mM). The ATP concentration in each well was measured by using ATP Bioluminescence Assay Kit CLS II (Roche) following manufacturer's instructions. The assay was performed in a HTS system (96-well format).

2.19. Adenine nucleotide measurement (ATP/ADP/AMP)

ATP, ADP and AMP levels in HepG2 cells were measured by HPLC, as previously described [43]. Energy charge was calculated as $([ATP] + 0.5 [ADP])/([ATP] + [ADP] + [AMP])$.

2.20. Measurement of malondialdehyde (MDA) levels

Oxidative damage of lipids was evaluated by the formation of a thiobarbituric acid (TBA) adduct of malondialdehyde (MDA) and then separated by HPLC, as previously described [43].

2.21. Caspase-like colorimetric activity assay

To measure caspase 3- and 9-like activity, aliquots of cell extracts containing 25 μg (for caspase 3) and 50 μg (for caspase 9) of protein were incubated in a reaction buffer containing 25 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 10 % sucrose, 10 mM DTT, 0.1 % CHAPS and 100 μM caspase substrate (Ac-DEVDpNA for caspase 3 or Ac-LEHDpNA for caspase 9 (Calbiochem, Billerica, MA) for 2 h at 37 °C. Caspase-like activities were determined by following the detection of the chromophore p-nitroanilide after cleavage from the labeled substrate Ac-DEVD-p-nitroanilide or Ac-LEHD-pnitroanilide, as previously described [43].

2.22. Cell mass measurements

The sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay was used for cell mass determination based on the measurement of cellular protein content [30], as previously described [43].

2.23. NAD⁺/NADH measurements

Intracellular NAD⁺ and NADH levels were measured using the NAD/NADH-Glo™ assay (G9071, Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.24. NADP⁺/NADPH measurements

Intracellular NADP⁺ and NADPH levels were measured using the NADP/NADPH-Glo™ assay (G9081, Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.25. Intracellular ATP levels

Intracellular ATP levels were measured using CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay (G7570, Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.26. Nuclear magnetic resonance

During the antioxidant treatment, 200 μL media aliquots were collected at 0, 8, 24, 36 and 48 h and kept at -80 °C for extracellular lactate buildup analysis. At the end of the antioxidant incubation period, cells were washed with PBS and collected by solvent scraping with a methanol/chloroform/water (1:1:0.1) [31]. The extracts were centrifuged and the pellet containing protein and lipids were separated. The aqueous extracts and media aliquots were analyzed by NMR, as previously described [43].

2.27. Extracellular acidification measurements

Extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) was measured at 37 °C using the Seahorse XF Glycolysis Stress Test Kit in the Seahorse XFe96 Extracellular Flux Analyzer (Agilent Scientific Instruments, California, USA) following manufacturer's instructions, as previously described [43].

2.28. Statistics

Data were analyzed in GraphPad Prism 8.0.2 software (GraphPad Software, Inc.), with all results being expressed as means \pm SEM for the number of experiments indicated. The student's *t*-test for comparison of

two means, and one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test was used to compare more than two groups with one independent variable were used in data analysis. Significance was accepted with **P* < 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.0005, *****P* < 0.0001.

3. Results

3.1. AntiOxClN₆ decreased mitochondrial oxidative stress-induced cell damage

We previously demonstrated that mitochondria-targeted antioxidant based on caffeic (AntiOxClN₆) acid (Fig. 1A) conferred cell death protection in different *in vitro* cell models [22,24]. In line with previous results, menadione (50 μM , 4 h) induced a reduction of about 50 % in the metabolic activity of HepG2 cells, an event that was significantly prevented by increasing concentrations of AntiOxClN₆ (Fig. 1B). In fact, AntiOxClN₆ dose-dependently counteract mitochondrial oxidative stress-induced cell damage promoted by pro-oxidant menadione (MEN, a ROS-generating molecule that triggers cell death at high concentrations), reaching the best effect at the maximal non-lethal concentration (Fig. 1B).

3.2. AntiOxClN₆ antioxidant capacity is due to a mitochondrial ROS-mediated upregulation of HepG2 cell's antioxidant defense system

The antioxidant properties of AntiOxClN₆, which conferred death protection in human HepG2 cells and differentiated SH-SY5Y cells, are often accompanied by a mild increase in ROS levels [24]. Using the fluorescent reporter MitoSOX, we quantified mitochondrial superoxide anion levels. We confirmed here that AntiOxClN₆ induced a transient increase in the MitoSOX oxidation rate in the first 24 h (~180 %), returning to control levels at the 48 h time-point (Fig. 1C). As transient increase in mtROS production may signaling for cytoprotective antioxidant pathways necessary for cell homeostasis maintenance [32], we next evaluated several components of cellular antioxidant (non-enzymatic and enzymatic) defense system. Interestingly, AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) significantly increased the intracellular vitamin E (α -tocopherol) content (Fig. 1D) and GSH/GSSG ratio (Fig. 1E). Moreover, AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) also significantly increased glutathione reductase activity (GR) (Fig. 1F), while no alterations were observed in the glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity (Fig. 1G). Similarly, AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) significantly increased γ -glutamylcysteine synthetase (g-GCS) (Fig. 1H) and Thioredoxin 1 (Trx1) (Fig. 1I) protein levels. Although superoxide dismutase 1 (SOD1) content was not altered in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells (Fig. 1J), we observed that AntiOxClN₆ increased total SOD activity (Fig. 1K). On the other hand, AntiOxClN₆ significantly decreased catalase (CAT) (Fig. 1L) levels with a non-significant decrease in activity (Fig. 1M). The data suggest that, although AntiOxClN₆ up-regulated non-enzymatic endogenous antioxidant defense systems, it cannot operate in ROS clearance (mainly H₂O₂).

3.3. AntiOxClN₆ decreased mitochondrial oxygen consumption rates and polarization in HepG2 cells

Although mitochondria-targeted antioxidants accumulate within the mitochondrial matrix and display cytoprotective effects, their beneficial effects on mitochondrial metabolism and physiology are still not clear. To further understand the impact of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) on mitochondrial oxygen consumption rates (OCR) of HepG2 cells (Fig. 2A), we examined the proportions of various parameters, including ATP-synthase linked respiration, reserve capacity, proton leak, and non-mitochondrial respiration (Fig. 2B). AntiOxClN₆ reduced the basal (70.8 %) (Fig. 2C) and ATP production-linked (71.0 %) OCR (Fig. 2D) and significantly decreased maximal (57.3 %) OCR (Fig. 2E) and spare respiratory capacity (46.11 %) (Fig. 2F), while no significant changes were observed in proton leak-related (82.2 %) OCR (Fig. 2G). Mitochondrial

Fig. 2. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on mitochondrial oxygen consumption and membrane potential of HepG2 cells. (A) Representative image of oxygen consumption rate (OCR) measurement in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h). (B) The proportion of OCR due to ATP synthase, proton leak and non-mitochondrial oxygen consumption. The proportion of above three indices plus reserve capacity is quantified by taking “highest” OCR as 100 % (3rd point after BAM15 injection). Several respiratory parameters were evaluated: (C) cellular basal OCR; (D) ATP production-linked OCR; (E) maximal OCR; (F) spare respiratory capacity; and (G) proton leak OCR. (H) Representative background-corrected image of HepG2 cells stained with the fluorescent cation TMRM and Hoechst 33342 in cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) in the presence or absence of oligomycin (2 μ M; 30 min). The TMRM and Hoechst fluorescence intensity was color-coded to red and blue, respectively. (I) Average mitochondrial TMRM fluorescence intensity was calculated from the images. Data are mean \pm SEM of 3–4 independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student’s *t*-test to compare two mean values and the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * ($p < 0.05$). Significant differences between AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M) in the presence or absence of oligomycin are indicated by # ($p < 0.05$). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

stress induction caused by alterations in mtROS levels or in oxygen consumption impact mitochondrial homeostasis and directly can affect mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi$ m) [33]. So, we analyzed the alterations in $\Delta\Psi$ m caused by AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) accumulation in HepG2 cells by fluorescence microscopy using the fluorescent tetramethyl rhodamine (TMRM) dye (Fig. 2H). Treatment with oligomycin (2 μ M, 30 min), an ATP-synthase inhibitor, resulted in a significant increase in TMRM fluorescence (207.1 %) (Fig. 2I). Conversely, AntiOxClN₆ *per se* significantly decreased TMRM fluorescence (61.8 %) and significantly prevented the oligomycin-induced hyperpolarization (by 118.7 %) (Fig. 2I). Overall, under non-lethal conditions, AntiOxClN₆ impairs mitochondrial bioenergetics of HepG2 cells.

3.4. AntiOxClN₆ decreased mitochondrial DNA copy number, mRNA gene transcript and mitochondrial markers protein levels of HepG2 cells

Mitochondria are dynamic organelles constantly changing their content according to their metabolic demands. Consequently, we assessed the impact of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) on HepG2 mitochondrial (morphological and functional) markers. We observe that AntiOxClN₆ significantly decreased mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) copy number (70.1 %), a marker of mitochondrial mass (Fig. 3A). Additionally, AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) significantly decreased mRNA transcript levels of the master regulator of mitochondrial biogenesis *PPARGC1A* (77.2 %), while no alterations in mRNA levels for *TFAM* (84.5 %) and *GAPBA* (85.3 %) transcripts were observed when compared to untreated

cells (Fig. 3B). Interestingly, AntiOxClN₆ treatment significantly increased mRNA levels for *NR1F1* (157.7 %) (Fig. 3B). Moreover, measurement of mRNA levels encoding mitochondrial OXPHOS complexes transcripts showed a significant decrease in mitochondrial encoded complex I *ND5* (69.9 %) and *CY5C* (60.0 %) subunits (Fig. 3C). A slight decrease in mRNA levels for *COX4i* (78.8 %) subunit (Fig. 3C) was also observed, although the differences were not statistically significant. On the other hand, mRNA levels of complex III *UQCRC2* (97.1 %), and complex V *ATP5G1* (115.3 %) subunits remained unchanged (Fig. 3C). Next, mRNA transcripts levels of mitochondrial dynamics hallmarks were evaluated. AntiOxClN₆ significantly decreased transcript levels of the fusion key player optic atrophy 1 (*OPA1*) (59.4 %) (Fig. 3D). AntiOxClN₆ also displayed a slight decrease in mRNA levels for mitofusin 2 (*MFN2*) (66.8 %) (Fig. 3D), although the differences were not statistically significant. Conversely, the mRNA level of fission key player *FIS1* (131.5 %) was slightly increased, although the differences were not statistically significant (Fig. 3D). Finally, we evaluated whether the decrease in mitochondrial morphology- and dynamics-related gene expression and mtDNA copy number were associated with altered expression levels of different mitochondrial proteins markers. Western blot analysis revealed that AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) significantly decreased complex V ATP5G1 subunit (74.0 %), IM (77.8 %), voltage-dependent anion channel (VDAC) (61.3 %), and cytochrome *c* (71.6 %) protein content (Fig. 3E). However, CypD protein content (91.1 %) remained unchanged in HepG2-treated cells (Fig. 3E). Altogether, the data suggest that AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) compromise the

Fig. 3. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on mitochondrial mass, biogenesis, and structural markers in HepG2. (A) mtDNA copy number of HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h). mtDNA copy number was based on the amplification of cytochrome *B* (encoded on the mitochondrial genome) and β-2-microglobulin (encoded on the nuclear genome) ratio. mRNA levels of (B) mitochondrial biogenesis markers *PPARGC1A*, *TFAM*, *NRF1* and *GAPBA*, (C) OXPHOS markers *ND5*, *COX4I1*, *UQCRC2*, *CYSC* and *ATP5G1*, and (D) mitochondrial dynamics markers *FIS1*, *MFN2* and *OPA1* genes in cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h). The results were normalized to TBP, HPRT1 transcript levels. (E) Representative Western blot result and protein content of ATP5A, UQCRC1, VDAC 1 + 2, CypD, Cyt C in whole-cell homogenates treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h). This blot was inverted and contrast-optimized for visualization purposes. Quantification of the bands was performed using the original blots. Quantification of protein content was normalized in each lane to total protein levels (Ponceau S labeling). (F) AntiOxClN₆ effects on mitochondrial ATP-formation. Mitochondrial complex I-driven ATP synthesis rate of rotenone-enhanced sensitivity of osteosarcoma cybrid cells carrying the 11778 mutation (HCT22 cells) treated with AntiOxClN₆ (3 µM; 24 h) in the absence or presence of rotenone (0.03 µM; 2 h). Papaverine (30 µM; 24 h), which was identified to reverse the rotenone sensitivity of the mutant cells, was used as a positive control. Data are mean ± SEM of 3–4 independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). Mitochondrial complex I-driven ATP synthesis data are means ± SD of three independent experiments and are expressed as µM ATP synthesized/min. Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student's *t*-test to compare two mean values and the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * (*p* < 0.05), *** (*p* < 0.0005), **** (*p* < 0.0001). Significant differences between rotenone in the absence or presence of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM) or papaverine (30 µM; 24 h) in osteosarcoma cybrid cells carrying the 11778 mutation (HCT22 cells) are indicated by ### (*p* < 0.0005).

mitochondrial network.

3.5. AntiOxClN₆ decreased mitochondrial ATP production but not the overall HepG2 cell's energy charge or proliferative capacity

Altered mitochondrial respiration and/or mitochondrial morphology are often associated with an impaired mitochondrial ATP production, in particular complex I-driven ATP production. Thus, we next investigated the effects of AntiOxClN₆ on complex I ATP-driven synthesis, using osteosarcoma cybrid cells carrying the Leber hereditary optic neuropathy (LHON)-associated 11778 mutation. These cells presented an increased susceptibility to the inhibitory effect of rotenone [34], which significantly decreased complex I-driven ATP synthesis (Fig. 3F). As expected, papaverine (30 µM; 24 h), significantly prevented the rotenone-induced decrease in ATP synthesis (Fig. 3F). Interestingly, the results showed that AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h) significantly decreased complex I-driven ATP synthesis rate (71.6 %) (Fig. 3F) but also synergistically promote the rotenone-induced decrease in the ATP production rate (Fig. 3F). Next, the energy state of HepG2 cells treated with AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h) was evaluated by measuring the intracellular AMP, ADP and ATP

levels, and energy charge. The AMP, ADP and ATP (Fig. 4A), as well as, AMP/ATP (Fig. 4B) and ATP/ADP (Fig. 4C) ratios, or the cellular energy charge (Fig. 4D) remained unchanged after AntiOxClN₆ treatment. Next, we evaluated the effects of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h) on glycolytic ATP production. We observed that, as expected, 2-deoxy-D-glucose (2-DG), an inhibitor of glycolysis, significantly decreased ATP levels of HepG2 cells (Fig. 4E). Although AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h) did not alter intracellular ATP levels, it significantly aggravated the effect of 2-DG on intracellular ATP levels (Fig. 4E). The data suggest a more glycolytic-dependent ATP production in AntiOxClN₆-treated HepG2 cells. We also evaluated the cellular content of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) protein, as well as, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD), and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) systems, due to their key role on regulate cellular redox homeostasis and biosynthesis in living cells. Western blot analysis demonstrated that AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM; 48 h) significantly increased NADH/NAD⁺ (155.1 %) (Fig. 4F) but not the NADPH/NADP⁺ ratio (Fig. 4G) or G6PD protein content (92.1 %) (Fig. 4H). Finally, we evaluated the effect of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 µM) treatment on HepG2 proliferation by means of SRB absorbance. We observed that AntiOxClN₆ did not affect HepG2 cell

Fig. 4. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on adenosine nucleotides content, cell proliferation, malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and caspase-like activity of HepG2 cells. (A) ATP, ADP and AMP levels, (B) AMP/ATP and (C) ATP/ADP ratios and, (D) Energy charge $[\text{ATP} + 0.5 [\text{ADP}]]/([\text{ATP} + [\text{ADP}] + [\text{AMP}]])$ in HepG2 cells treated with AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). Data are mean \pm SEM of five independent assays performed, and the results are expressed as the pmol of adenosine nucleotides/ μg protein. (E) Intracellular ATP levels of HepG2 cells treated with 2-deoxyglucose (2-DG, 50 mM; 3 h) in the absence or presence of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). (F) NADPH/NAD⁺ and (G) NADH/NAD⁺ ratios in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). Data are mean \pm SEM of four independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). (H) Representative Western blot result and protein content of glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) and β -actin (cytosolic marker) in whole-cell homogenates treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). This blot was inverted and contrast-optimized for visualization purposes. Quantification of the bands was performed using the original blots. Level of protein levels in four different assays performed was normalized to β -actin levels and to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). (I) Time-dependent effect of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM) on HepG2 cell mass. Data are mean \pm SEM of five independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition ($t_0 = 100$ %). (J) Malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). Data are mean \pm SEM of four independent assays performed, and the results are expressed as pmol of MDA/ μg protein. (K) Caspase 9- and (L) Caspase 3-like activity in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h). Data are mean \pm SEM of five independent assays performed, and the results are expressed as nM of pNA released/ μg protein. Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student's *t*-test to compare two mean values. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * ($p < 0.05$). Significant differences in intracellular ATP levels between 2-DG in the absence or presence of AntiOxClN₆ are indicated by # ($p < 0.05$).

mass (Fig. 4I). Altogether, the data suggest that AntiOxClN₆ specifically inhibited mitochondrial complex I-driven ATP synthesis but does not affect the overall cellular energy charge or proliferative capacity.

3.6. AntiOxClN₆ did not induce pro-apoptotic lipid peroxidation and caspase activation hallmarks

Increased ROS levels produced by mitochondria combined with defective mitochondrial ATP production can lead to oxidative stress and trigger cell death due to mitochondrial disruption [35]. Consequently, we determined whether AntiOxClN₆ can induce lipid peroxidation or activate caspase-dependent cell death signaling pathways. The treatment with AntiOxClN₆ does not induce lipid peroxidation, measured as malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, in HepG2 cells (Fig. 4J). Likewise, AntiOxClN₆ treatment did not alter either caspase 9 (Fig. 4K) or caspase 3-like activity (Fig. 4L). The data suggest that HepG2 cells treated with AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) may adapt their cellular metabolism to maintain cellular energy homeostasis and proliferation capacity rather than activate caspase-dependent apoptotic cell death pathways.

3.7. AntiOxClN₆ increased HepG2 cells glycolytic flux

Mitochondrial functional abnormalities are often associated with pathophysiological increases in glycolytic fluxes [36]. Next, we assessed the effect of AntiOxClN₆ on cellular glycolytic fluxes by measuring glucose, lactate and alanine levels and production rates in HepG2 cells using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) significantly decreased glucose (Fig. 5A) and increased lactate levels (Fig. 5B), when compared to control. Consequently, AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) significantly increased glucose consumption (CTL; 0.06483 ± 0.012 , AntiOxClN₆; 0.08977 ± 0.008 mM/h) (Fig. 5C), increased lactate (CTL; 0.09460 ± 0.006 , AntiOxClN₆; 0.1381 ± 0.008 mM/h) (Fig. 5D) and alanine (Fig. 5E) production rates, compared to untreated cells. Lactate/Alanine ratio, an indirect indicator of increased glycolytic flux [37], was also significantly increased by AntiOxClN₆ treatment (Fig. 5F). To deepen our comprehension of the impact of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM ; 48 h) on the glycolytic flux of HepG2 cells, we assessed the extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) (Fig. 5G) and examined the proportions of various parameters, including glycolysis, glycolytic reserve and non-glycolytic capacity (Fig. 5H). Although AntiOxClN₆ slightly reduced the glycolytic capacity-associated ECAR (86.2 %)

Fig. 5. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on cellular energetic status of HepG2 cells. Representative nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) measurement spectrum of time-dependent (A) glucose (CTL: $R^2 = 0.80$; AntiOxClN₆: $R^2 = 0.88$) and (B) lactate levels (CTL: $R^2 = 0.93$; AntiOxClN₆: $R^2 = 0.94$) in HepG2 cells treated with AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M). The rate values were calculated by fitting the data with a linear regression equation. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) on (C) Glucose consumption, (D) Lactate and (E) Alanine production rates by NMR. (F) Lactate/Alanine ratio of HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h). (G) Representation of extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) measurement in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h). (H) ECAR is presented as a percentage of three components (glycolysis, glycolytic reserve, and non-glycolytic acidification), with the “highest” ECAR being set as the reference point at 100 % (3rd point after 2-DG injection). Several parameters were evaluated: (I) glycolytic capacity-associated ECAR, (J) glycolysis-associated ECAR, and (K) CO₂-linked ECAR. (L) Cellular energetic status of HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h). The average mitochondrial OCR was plotted against the average ECAR, which demonstrates a shift for a more glycolytic status in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells. (M) Metabolic potential of HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h). Stressed OCR and Stressed ECAR were differently affected by AntiOxClN₆ treatment. Data are mean \pm SEM of 3–4 different assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). NMR data are means \pm SEM of 6 independent experiments, and the results are expressed as mM of glucose consumed or lactate and alanine produced/hour. Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student’s *t*-test to compare two mean values and the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by *($p < 0.05$), **($p < 0.01$), ***($p < 0.0005$).

(Fig. 5I), glycolysis-associated ECAR (119.4 %) was significantly increased in AntiOxClN₆ HepG2-treated cells (Fig. 5J). Notably, we did not observe any alterations in CO₂-linked ECAR, suggesting that AntiOxClN₆ does not significantly affect the Krebs Cycle, the major source of mitochondrial CO₂ (Fig. 5K). Next, we plotted the average data of basal OCR against basal ECAR (Fig. 5L). This plot clearly showed that AntiOxClN₆ data points shifted towards a more glycolytic status (Fig. 5L). Finally, we determined the metabolic potential of AntiOxClN₆-treated HepG2 cells, i.e., measurement of the cells’ ability to meet an energy demand via mitochondrial respiration and glycolysis (increase of stressed OCR/ECAR over baseline OCR/ECAR) (Fig. 5M). AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) significantly decreased stressed OCR but not the stressed ECAR of HepG2 cells (Fig. 5M). Overall, the data suggest that mitochondrial functional and morphological abnormalities in AntiOxClN₆-treated HepG2 cells are paralleled by an increased glycolytic flux and a more glycolytic-dependent ATP production.

3.8. AntiOxClN₆ transiently decreased AMPK protein levels

AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) acts as a sensor of cellular energy levels and, therefore, controls several metabolic pathways by regulating ATP synthesis and consumption [38]. To further understanding the time-dependent effect of AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M) on cells’

energetic status, we evaluated the levels of Thr172-phosphorylated AMPK α (active form) and AMPK- α subunit protein in HepG2 cells by Western Blotting (Fig. 6A). Interestingly, AntiOxClN₆ induced a rapid (~58 %) and transient significant decrease in both P-AMPK- α and AMPK- α protein levels, which was maintained until the 24 h time-point, and returned to control levels at the 48 h time-point (Fig. 6A). The data suggest that AMPK may mediate the cellular metabolic reprogramming induced by the mitochondriotropic agent AntiOxClN₆.

3.9. AntiOxClN₆ increased glycolytic-related HKII, PKM and LDHA protein levels while decreased TCA cycle-related PDH protein content

Thus far, our observations have revealed that AntiOxClN₆ induces a metabolic reprogramming characterized by a reduction in mitochondrial metabolism, favoring a shift towards glycolysis-dependent ATP production. To further investigate this phenomenon, we evaluated the levels of key proteins involved in the glycolytic pathway and the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA cycle) using Western Blotting. AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μ M; 48 h) significantly increased the glycolytic-related proteins, including hexokinase (HKII) (329,8%), pyruvate kinase 2 (PKM) (121,8%) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDHA) (113,7%) (Fig. 6B). On the other hand, we observed a significant decrease in the protein levels of the pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) complex, which converts pyruvate

Fig. 6. Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on expression of glycolytic pathway proteins in HepG2 cells. (A) Time-dependent effect of AntiOxClN₆ on AMPKα and p-AMPKα protein levels in HepG2. Representative Western blot result and protein content of AMPKα, p-AMPKα and β-actin (cytosolic marker) in total fractions from cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM). Effect of AntiOxClN₆ on protein levels of glycolytic-related proteins. Representative Western blot result and protein content of (B) HKII, PKM2, LDH and (C) PDH-E2, PDH-E3bp, PDH-E1β and β-actin (cytosolic marker) in whole-cell homogenates from cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h). This blot was inverted and contrast-optimized for visualization purposes. Quantification of the bands was performed using the original blots. Quantification of protein levels in four independent assays performed was normalized to β-actin levels and to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). (D) Intracellular aspartate/alanine (Asp/Ala) ratio in HepG2 cells treated with vehicle (CTL) or AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h) measured by NMR. Data are means ± SEM of 6 independent experiments, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the Student's *t*-test to compare two mean values and the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * (*p* < 0.05).

into acetyl-CoA to fuel the TCA cycle. AntiOxClN₆ decreased the levels of PDH-E2 (63,4%) and PDH-E1β (55,0%), but not PDH-E3bp (83,5%) subunits (Fig. 6C) in HepG2 cells, when compared to control. Elevated levels of PKM2 protein can enhance glycolytic activity, consequently leading to an increased conversion of phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) to pyruvate, which can influence on the Aspartate/Alanine (Asp/Ala) ratio. Interestingly, we observed a reduction in the Asp/Ala ratio by AntiOxClN₆ (Fig. 6D), suggesting a dynamic interplay within the glycolytic. These results strengthened our hypothesis that AntiOxClN₆ (2.5 μM; 48 h) induces a metabolic remodeling in HepG2 to a more glycolytic status.

3.10. AntiOxClN₆ differentially affected A549 lung adenocarcinoma and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts viability

As mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming has been described as a potential target for cancer therapy [39,40], AntiOxClN₆ cytotoxic effects was also evaluated in lung-derived adenocarcinoma human A549 alveolar basal epithelial cells and normal human lung MRC-5 fibroblasts by means of the SRB assay. AntiOxClN₆ caused dose-dependent toxicity effects on both tumor A549 and non-tumor MRC-5 cells; however, those effects were more significant in A549 cells, when compared with MRC-5, and more noticeable at 48 h treatment (Fig. 7A). The data suggest that AntiOxClN₆ is more toxic to lung cancer cells than to non-cancer cells. For further assess the AntiOxClN₆ effects on anticancer drug cisplatin-induced damage, we select a concentration that significantly reduced cell mass of adenocarcinoma human A549 alveolar basal epithelial cells but not normal human lung MRC-5 fibroblasts (AntiOxClN₆, 3.1 μM; 48 h).

3.11. AntiOxClN₆, cisplatin (CIS) and sequential AntiOxClN₆/CIS treatments differentially affected mitochondrial ROS levels and pro-apoptotic phenotypes of lung A549 and MRC-5 cells

Following the data obtained in HepG2 cells on mitochondrial-induced oxidative stress, we investigated of the effects of treating cells with AntiOxClN₆ plus a sequential treatment with an anticancer drug, by measuring mitochondrial superoxide anion levels using the fluorescent reporter MitoSOX (Fig. 7B). In our experimental model and conditions, CIS (10 μM; 3 h) treatment did not impact on the MitoSOX oxidation rate of both A549 lung cancer cells and MRC-5 fibroblasts (Fig. 7B). However, AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) alone significantly increased MitoSOX oxidation rate in A549 and MRC-5 (Fig. 7B). Interestingly, the pre-treatment with AntiOxClN₆ significantly increased the effect of CIS on MitoSOX oxidation rate in A549 cells but not in normal lung fibroblasts (MRC-5 cells) (Fig. 7B). Then, CIS effects, when sequentially added to AntiOxClN₆, was also investigated in A549 lung cancer cells and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts regarding mitochondrial-related caspase-dependent apoptotic pathways, by measuring caspases 9-like activity (Fig. 7C). In our experimental model, CIS (10 μM; 18 h) treatment increased caspase-9-like activity in both A549 and MRC-5 cells (Fig. 7C). No alteration in caspase 9-like activity was observed in both cell lines when treated with AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) alone. Interestingly, pre-treatment of A549 cells with AntiOxClN₆ significantly increased the effects of CIS on caspase-9-like activity in, while it slightly inhibited the cytotoxic effect of in normal lung fibroblasts (MRC-5 cells) (Fig. 7C). Our results suggest that AntiOxClN₆ potentiate the CIS-induced effects on mtROS production and activation of pro-apoptotic pathways in lung cancer cells.

Fig. 7. Effect of AntiOxClN₆ on mitochondrial superoxide anion levels, caspase 9-like activity, and cell metabolic activity and mass in normal lung fibroblast MRC-5 and lung adenocarcinoma A549 cell lines. (A) Cell mass of MRC-5 and A549 cells cultured in the presence of increasing concentrations of AntiOxClN₆ for 24 h (left) or 48 h (right). (B) Variations on fluorescence signal of MitoSOX-oxidation products in MRC-5 and A549 cells treated with vehicle (CTL), or AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) in the absence or presence of cisplatin (10 μM; 3 h). (C) Caspase 9-like activity in MRC-5 and A549 cells treated with vehicle (CTL), or AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) in the absence or presence of cisplatin (10 μM; 18 h). Effects of AntiOxClN₆ on CIS-induced cytotoxicity in A549 lung cancer cells and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts. (D) Cell metabolic activity and (E) mass of MRC-5 and A549 cells treated with vehicle (CTL), or AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) in the absence or presence of cisplatin (10 μM; 24 h). Data are mean ± SEM of 5–6 independent assays performed, and the results were normalized to the control condition (CTL = 100 %). MitoSOX data are the mean ± SEM of 6 independent assays performed, and the results are expressed as MitoSOX fluorescence signals per cell mass. Statistics: The data obtained with AntiOxClN₆ was compared to CTL using the one-way ANOVA with Dunnett multiple comparison post-test to compare more than two groups with one independent variable or two-way ANOVA followed by Fisher's LSD test for multiple comparisons. Significant differences between the indicated conditions are indicated by * (p < 0.05), ** (p < 0.01), *** (p < 0.0005), **** (p < 0.0001). Significant differences between AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM) in the absence or presence of cisplatin are indicated by # (p < 0.05), ## (p < 0.01).

3.12. AntiOxClN₆ differentially interfered with CIS-induced cytotoxicity on A549 lung cancer cells and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts

Final endpoints for oxidative stress-induced toxicity in A549 tumor and MRC-5 non-tumor cells were evaluated by measuring alterations in cell metabolic activity and mass by using the resazurin reduction (Fig. 7D) and SRB assays (Fig. 7E), respectively. In our experimental model, a non-significant decrease on cell metabolic viability (Fig. 7D) and mass (Fig. 7E) was observed in both A549 lung cancer cells and MRC-5 lung fibroblasts incubated with CIS (10 μM; 24 h), when compared with untreated cells. AntiOxClN₆ (3.1 μM; 24 h) alone did not alter metabolic activity of both A549 and MRC-5 cells (Fig. 7D) but significantly decreased A549 cell mass (Fig. 7E). Remarkably, the sequential treatment of AntiOxClN₆ with CIS did not potentiate the CIS-induced cytotoxicity in MRC-5 fibroblasts but significantly increased the CIS-induced cytotoxicity in A549 cell, (Fig. 7D) and mass (Fig. 7E). The data suggest that pre-treating cancer cells with the mitochondriotropic agent AntiOxClN₆ may potentiate cell death induced by cisplatin.

4. Discussion

Mitochondria are heterogeneous organelles that play key roles in controlling redox homeostasis, antioxidant defense mechanisms, and energetic demands [7,41]. The modulation of mitochondrial activity by polyphenols has been extensively described [5]. Consequently, several TPP⁺-linked mitochondria-targeted polyphenolic derivatives were developed with different cell models, in part to destabilize mitochondrial function and promote antiproliferative effects [11–15,42]. In light of the absence of FDA- or EMA-approved mitochondria-targeted

molecules and the emergence of drug resistance in various cancer therapies, attributed to the distinct metabolic profiles of different cells, ongoing efforts are focused on the development of drugs that integrate the induction of mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming with the ability to generate ROS. This innovative approach aims to achieve more selective and efficient anticancer effects. By combining these two mechanisms, the therapeutic agents can target specific metabolic vulnerabilities of cancer cells and simultaneously inducing oxidative stress to impair their survival and proliferation, while also decreasing their capacity to metastasize. The development of such dual-action drugs holds great potential in advancing the field of anticancer therapeutics. We previously developed a mitochondria-targeted antioxidant (AntiOxClN₆) by linking the caffeic acid antioxidant core to TPP⁺ through a 10-carbon aliphatic chain (TPP-C10). Although AntiOxClN₆ antioxidant activity has been described [22,24], how the mitochondriotropic compound interact with normal and cancer cells energy metabolism remain unknown. In this context, this study aimed to clarify the cellular mechanisms of action underlying the AntiOxClN₆-induced cytotoxic vs. cytoprotective effects to potentiate its therapeutic application.

The present study showed that AntiOxClN₆ conferred cell death protection in HepG2 cells against damage caused by subsequent oxidative stress, which was accompanied by cell's up-regulation of non-enzymatic (GSH, vit. E) and enzymatic (γ-GCS, SOD, GR and TRx1) endogenous antioxidant defense systems. The observed transient increase in mtROS levels probably drives the activation of endogenous ROS-dependent protective pathways in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells. These results are in line with our previous observations suggesting that mitochondria-targeted phenolic antioxidant AntiOxClN₄ (TPP-C6-CA)-induced transient increase in mtROS levels may lead to activation of

Nrf2. Under these circumstances, cysteine residues on Keap1 become oxidized or modified, prompting Nrf2's translocation to the nucleus. Once in the nucleus, Nrf2 activates the transcription of genes responsible for antioxidants and detoxification, including γ -GCS, SOD, GR, and TRx1 [43]. Among these enzymes, SOD plays a pivotal role by efficiently converting superoxide radicals into H_2O_2 . Although AntiOxClN₆ effects directly impact cells' antioxidant defense systems, ROS (mainly H_2O_2) clearance is ineffective, as protein amount and activity of CAT, the major enzyme responsible for catalyzing the reduction of H_2O_2 to water were decreased in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells. Overall, these findings point to a sophisticated and orchestrated response to oxidative stress facilitated by AntiOxClN₆, resulting in an increased defense against cellular damage that allow "normal" cells to survive upon cisplatin treatment, while cancer cells not.

Altered mitochondrial morphology and function are often associated with alterations in the production of ROS levels [32]. In fact, AntiOxClN₆ significantly decreased mitochondrial OCR and polarization ($\Delta\psi$), which was paralleled by a significant decrease in mtDNA copy number. Moreover, expression of PGC1- α and mitochondrial fusion-related genes were significantly decreased in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells. Consequently, the expression of OXPHOS-related genes and protein levels of mitochondrial markers were significantly reduced, which culminated in a decreased capacity in mitochondrial complex I-driven ATP production. Notwithstanding, the observed decrease in ATP5A (ATP synthase subunit alpha) levels was not accompanied by alterations in the mRNA levels of ATP5G1 (ATP synthase subunit gamma 1). As these subunits serve distinct roles within the mitochondrial ATP synthase complex, divergence facing diverse cellular signals, stressors, or treatments can be attributed to various factors: a) changes in the transcription or translation of the ATP5A gene or specific post-translational modifications targeting ATP5A; and b) conditions leading to ATP5A degradation via proteolytic pathways or other degradation mechanisms may not necessarily impact ATP5G1 to the same extent and result in decreased ATP5A levels without affecting ATP5G1. On the other hand, AntiOxClN₆ did not affect the pool of adenine nucleotides or the overall cellular energy charge and proliferation. Similarly, MDA levels as well as pro-apoptotic caspase activity were not altered in AntiOxClN₆-treated cells. Interestingly, AntiOxClN₆ significantly increased NADH/NAD⁺ ratio while no alteration in CO₂-linked ECAR was observed, which led us to hypothesize that AntiOxClN₆ does not significantly affect the Krebs Cycle and these cells became more dependent on glycolysis, as NAD⁺ is an essential cofactor in the regulation of this metabolic pathway. In fact, AntiOxClN₆ significantly increased glucose consumption, and lactate and alanine production rates, while improving lactate/alanine ratio, an indirect indicator of the glycolytic flux [37]. Likewise, AntiOxClN₆ increased glycolytic-related ECAR. The plotted ECAR vs. OCR confirmed an increased extracellular acidification and a shift of the metabolic profile towards a more glycolytic status, which significantly reduced the HepG2 cells metabolic potential. These alterations were followed by a transient decrease in Thr172-phosphorylated AMPK (p-AMPK- α) and AMPK- α protein levels as result of increase in AMP/ATP ratio, which culminate in a significant increment in the levels of glycolytic-related proteins (HKII, PKM2 and LDHA), while decreasing PDH complex content and the Asp/Ala ratio. Pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) complex is extremely important for mitochondrial metabolism, as it guarantees the supply of acetyl-CoA to the TCA cycle, while HKII catalyzes the first committed step in glucose metabolism by phosphorylating glucose [44]. We observed that the decrease in PDH and increase in lactate LDHA resulted in lactate accumulation. This finding aligns with elevated levels of PKM2 protein that enhance glycolytic activity, consequently leading to an increased conversion of phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) to pyruvate, with a direct impact on Asp/Ala ratio.

DecylTPP-based mitochondria-targeted antioxidants showed so far a mixed success since the presence of a TPP⁺ moiety could impair the insulant properties of the in the inner mitochondrial membrane (MIM) or compromise its structure that result in mitochondrial function

dysregulation [45,46], forcing cells to accelerate glycolysis [47]. Our findings align with recent studies that have demonstrated the inhibitory effect of a mitochondria-targeted antioxidant composed of gallic acid linked by an ester function (GA-TPP⁺-C10) on mitochondrial respiration. Specifically, GA-TPP⁺-C10 was shown to decrease OCR during both basal and maximal respiration. Moreover, in breast cancer cell lines, GA-TPP⁺-C10 exhibited inhibitory effects on complex I-dependent respiration. As a compensatory response, these cells exhibited the accumulation of hypoxia-inducible factor 1-alpha (HIF-1 α), increased glycolysis, and a subsequent inhibition of cancer cell death [11]. Similarly, MitoQ10 and MitoE10 were described as able to destabilize CI and/or ETC super-complexes, lowering CI/ETC activity, mitochondrial oxygen consumption, and ATP generation probably by reducing MIM fluidity, a process that can be rewarded by the activation of glycolytic ATP generation, preventing energy crisis and cell death [47]. Although the mentioned effects were only described at relatively high (μ M) concentrations, our results also provide evidence that decylTPP based mitochondria-targeted antioxidants can be linked to these events at concentrations (maximal non-lethal) with remarkable antioxidant effects.

Redirecting cellular energy metabolism towards glycolysis has emerged as a potential therapeutic strategy with promising outcomes in various health conditions, including hypertension, congestive heart failure, diabetes, and cancer. Metabolic remodeling by cancer cells to decrease their reliance on glycolysis is an important factor that explains drug-resistance to therapies [17]. For instance, remodeling mitochondrial function (increased mitochondrial mass and OXPHOS), is a described mechanism used to cancer cells resist to cisplatin treatment in NSCLC [20]. We observed that AntiOxClN₆ sensitized A549 (adenocarcinoma human alveolar basal epithelial) cells for CIS-induced apoptotic cell death, while may afford protection against CIS-induced effects on lung MRC-5 (normal human lung) fibroblasts due to a redox preconditioning [48]. Similarly, several other TPP⁺-linked mitochondria-targeted polyphenolic derivatives (MitoResveratrol; MitoCurcumin; MitoQuercetin; Mito-Honokiol; Mito-Ionidamine and MitoGentisic) have shown to destabilize mitochondrial function exhibiting anti-proliferative effects rather than a cytoprotective activity on different cell models [11–15,42]. The lung cancer heterogeneity marked by the different metabolic profile is the main obstacle in cancer therapy. A large unbalanced production of ROS (namely superoxide anion or hydrogen peroxide) that stimulate cell proliferation and promote genetic instability are often observed in advanced stage tumors [49], so new drugs combining ROS-generating ability together with a mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming can be relevant for adjuvant therapy with other anticancer molecules.

In conclusion, our work describes for the first time the potential mechanism of action behind the beneficial and detrimental effects of AntiOxClN₆, suggesting that the antioxidant core (CA) of AntiOxClN₆ is accountable for the ROS-dependent activation of cytoprotective pathways. In contrast, the length and hydrophobicity of the alkyl linker (C10-TPP⁺) play a crucial role in compromising mitochondrial oxygen consumption, membrane potential, morphology, and ATP production. AntiOxClN₆-induced mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming and activation of glycolytic ATP generation to prevent energy crisis, combined with AntiOxClN₆ ROS-generating ability can be used to sensitize lung cancer cells to anticancer drugs that generate mitochondrial oxidative stress, such as cisplatin (Fig. 8). Understanding such mechanisms is crucial to potentiate the therapeutic application of AntiOxClN₆ towards specific pathological conditions, such as lung cancer.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Paulo J. Oliveira and Fernanda Borges are cofounders of the CNC-UP spin-off company MitoTAG (Coimbra, Portugal). This SME had no involvement in the data collection, analysis and interpretation, writing

Fig. 8. Proposed mechanism by which mitochondria-targeted hydroxycinnamic acid antioxidant AntiOxCIN₆ impacts cellular metabolism and induces mitochondrial remodeling in human hepatocyte-like and lung cancer cells. Treatment with AntiOxCIN₆ (2.5 μM) for 48 h demonstrated a significant protective effect against mitochondrial oxidative stress-induced cellular damage. This effect was attributed to the upregulation of the antioxidant defense system in HepG2 cells. However, it should be noted that AntiOxCIN₆ treatment negatively impacted mitochondrial function, morphology, and ATP production. AntiOxCIN₆-treated cells trigger an adaptive survival program by accelerating glycolysis through the upregulation of the cellular transcriptional machinery, such as HKII, PKM2 and LDHA, and glycolytic-dependent ATP production, which contributes to an increase in the extracellular acidification rate and lactate levels. The AntiOxCIN₆-induced mitochondrial metabolic reprogramming, combined with AntiOxCIN₆ mild pro-oxidant effect can be relevant for cancer therapy. AntiOxCIN₆ pre-treatment sensitized A549 cancer cells for CIS-induced apoptotic cell death, while AntiOxCIN₆ may induce metabolic changes or a redox pre-conditioning on lung MRC-5 fibroblasts that may afford protection against CIS-induced effects. The scheme highlights the mechanism of action behind beneficial and detrimental effects of decylTPP-derived mitochondriotropic antioxidant AntiOxCIN₆. AntiOxCIN₆ length and hydrophobicity of the alkyl linker (*i.e.* C10-TPP⁺) is likely the driving force for mitochondrial and cellular toxicity and the antioxidant core (*i.e.* caffeic acid) is responsible for the observed ROS-dependent activation of cytoprotective pathways. AntiOxCIN₆ dual effects could best be used as a sensitizing strategy in combination with other anticancer treatments to potentiate lung cancer therapy.

of the manuscript, and in the decision to submit the manuscript for publication.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Author contribution

RA and JT performed the experiments. FB, SB and, FC designed and synthesized the mitochondria-targeted antioxidant. LCT and JGJ performed the NMR experiments. IB performed the HPLC experiments. KS and VAS performed the experiments with lung cells. SD and GAC performed the experiments with cybrid cells. FB, PO, RA, CM and JT analyzed the data. RA, CM and JT wrote the manuscript. JT and PJO supervised the research. PJO and FB revised the manuscript. FB, PJO and JT were responsible for funding acquisition.

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